

LLM Adoption Recommendations for Industrial Software Development Practices

Thank you for participating in our survey. My name is Krishna Ronanki. I, together with 3 other researchers from the University of Gothenburg, Sweden are conducting a study on the use of Large Language Models (LLM) to assist users in Software Engineering (SE) activities in industrial contexts. The objective of this survey is to validate 8 statements about LLMs.

By participating in this survey, you acknowledge that your responses will be used for research purposes only and will remain anonymous. No personal details will be collected, and only the research team will have access to your responses. Data will be securely stored for a minimum of five years and then destroyed. The analysis will involve aggregating responses for patterns and trends, with findings reported in an anonymised, aggregated format.

Your completion of the questionnaire indicates your informed consent to participate in the research. At any point in time during the survey, you can withdraw your consent by simply not submitting your responses or closing the browser window. If you have any questions or concerns about the study, please feel free to contact (krishna.ronanki@gu.se).

Please read each question carefully before responding. You will be asked to rate your agreement with the presented statement on a scale of 1-5, where 1 is strongly disagree, 2 is somewhat disagree, 3 is neutral, 4 is somewhat agree and 5 is strongly agree. Once again, thank you for your participation.

1. In which industry do you currently work?

- Software / IT
- Automotive
- Logistics
- Healthcare
- Finance
- Manufacturing
- Education
- Government
- Other

2. How do you rate yourself in Prompt Engineering (knowledge about few-shot prompting, chain-of-thought prompting and prompt patterns) on a scale of 1-5, 1 being a novice, 2 being intermediate, 3 being competent, 4 being proficient and 5 being an expert?

1	2	3	4	5
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3. Do you/your organisation work with an enterprise version of any LLM tools (for example, Microsoft Copilot, Github Copilot, ChatGPT)?

- Yes
- No

4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"It is beneficial to use the LLMs as assistants with human oversight rather than try and automate the task using the LLMs."

1	2	3	4	5
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5. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"When using LLMs as AI assistants, it is better to prioritise the usefulness of the LLMs' outputs rather than output accuracy (for example, even if the output is not 100% accurate, you can use some parts of the output to enhance the quality of the task that needs to be done)."

1	2	3	4	5
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6. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"The relevant stakeholders' satisfaction should be used as part of the LLM-generated outputs evaluation criteria (for example, developers and testers' satisfaction with the generated feature-level artefacts and customers' satisfaction for high-level requirements)."

1	2	3	4	5
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7. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"It is not beneficial to use any task-specific fine-tuned LLMs like GitHub Copilot for tasks they were not designed for (like generating user stories), even if they are technically capable of generating the requested artefacts."

1	2	3	4	5
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8. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"It is crucial to develop and implement human oversight and validation mechanisms while using LLMs' assistance for any task (for example, the user needs to ensure the accuracy, relevance, and quality of the output generated by the LLM and be accountable for it)."

1	2	3	4	5
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9. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"There is a need to create room for incorporating LLMs into business processes by restructuring (parts of) them (for example, LLMs will be primarily responsible for generating or improving low-level artefacts like user stories, code snippets, and documentation while humans will be primarily responsible for high-level artefacts like epics and features, designing architecture and workflows, and quality control)."

1	2	3	4	5
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10. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statement, using a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents 'Strongly Disagree' and 5 represents 'Strongly Agree':

"Knowledge-sharing activities like seminars and specialised training about prompt engineering are crucial for the users of the LLMs"

1	2	3	4	5
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